

COMPARING LUNAR THERMAL INFRARED INSTRUMENTS FOR COMPOSITIONAL INTERPRETATION. K. A. Shirley¹, H. Pieris², P. Hayne², K. L. Donaldson Hanna³, and N. E. Bowles¹, ¹AOPP, University of Oxford, UK (katherine.shirley@physics.ox.ac.uk), ²University of Colorado Boulder, USA, ³University of Central Florida, USA

Introduction: With the increase in lunar missions, there has also been an increase in thermal infrared instrumentation development for the Moon (e.g. Lunar Compact Infrared Imaging System (L-CIRiS) [1], Lunar Vulkan Imaging and Spectroscopy Explorer CIRiS (Lunar-VISE CIRiS) [2], Lunar Thermal Mapper (LTM) [3]). These instruments build on the heritage of the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Diviner Lunar Radiometer instrument [4], which has returned an invaluable thermal dataset for the lunar surface. Diviner measures surface temperature from its broadband channels and returns compositional information from its three narrow band channels, and these capabilities will be duplicated in the new instruments.

L-CIRiS is a multispectral imaging radiometer that has been selected for a NASA landed mission near the lunar south pole as part of Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) task order CP-22 [1]. It has four channels, three focused on mineralogy and one broad-band for temperature determination (Table 1). LV-CIRiS is the same type of instrument, but tailored for the Lunar-VISE payload that will land on the Gruithuisen domes, a silicic volcanic feature as part of CLPS task order CP-21 [2]. Therefore the mineralogy bands are shifted to shorter wavelengths. Both instruments will be on landed missions allowing for some of the first ground based measurements of thermal and compositional properties.

Narrow Band Centers (μm)	Instrument			
	Diviner	LTM	L-CIRiS	LV-CIRiS
		7.0		
		7.25		7.25
		7.5	7.5	7.5
	7.8	7.75	7.78	7.8
		8.0		
	8.2	8.25	8.28	
		8.5		
		8.75		
		9.0		
		9.5		
		10.0		

Table 1. Mineralogy focused narrow band position centers for the thermal infrared instruments.

LTM was originally flown on the Lunar Trailblazer mission, launched and lost in 2025. It is an orbital instrument with Diviner heritage, but with a larger set (11) of mineralogical bands to better define the range of compositions on the Moon. While Lunar

Trailblazer was lost, LTM will be reflown on the upcoming Ultra-Compact Imaging Spectrometer for the Moon (UCIS-Moon) mission [5]. Here we have done a quick comparison to demonstrate the utility of these instruments in compositional determination, how they are tailored per mission, and how they will cross-compare.

Methods: Laboratory spectra used in this comparison come from [6,7] and include Apollo regolith samples and terrestrial volcanic samples. The volcanic samples were chosen to represent possible materials at the Gruithuisen domes and not represented in the Apollo sample set. The filter responses for each instrument were multiplied with the laboratory spectra to create the instrument resolution data for comparison.

We also calculated the Christiansen feature (CF) value for each of the down-sampled spectra as the primary indicator of composition as established by Diviner. The CF value was determined by fitting a parabola to the three bands and finding the position of the emissivity maximum as is done for Diviner [8]. For LTM, which has many more bands, a cubic fit was used to calculate the CF value based on the methods of [9].

Figure 1. Laboratory emissivity spectrum of rhyolite (black [7]) overlain with its resolution in each thermal instrument. As a “highly silicic” composition, its CF is ~7.2 μm which is only captured by LTM and LV-CIRiS, which were designed for that purpose.

Spectrum Resolution	CF value (μm)
Laboratory	7.22
Diviner	8.60
LTM	7.20
L-CIRiS	6.65
LV-CIRiS	7.23

Table 2. Calculated CF values for the rhyolite spectra shown in Fig. 1. Only LTM and LV-CIRiS give reasonable values.

Results: Figure 1 shows the laboratory and down-sampled spectra for a rhyolitic sample. Rhyolite is not a common composition for the Moon, therefore only the LTM and LV-CIRiS instruments are developed to characterize this sample, while the others are designed for whole Moon coverage (including more mafic compositions) or the poles, which are also not as felsic. This optimization is also shown in how the CF values are calculated for this spectrum (Table 2).

Figure 2 shows a selection of Apollo samples from [6] with their down-sampled resolutions. Here we can see how the orbital instruments are well suited to the more common compositions likely to be encountered when mapping the lunar surface (Table 3).

Figure 2. Laboratory emissivity spectra of Apollo samples overlain with their thermal infrared resolution.

Spectral Resolution	Apollo 67701 CF (μm)	Apollo 15201 CF (μm)	Apollo 79221 CF (μm)
Laboratory	8.10	8.17	8.38
Diviner	8.19	8.33	8.40
LTM	8.13	8.24	8.40
L-CIRiS	7.88	7.98	8.02
LV-CIRiS	7.53	7.61	7.65

Table 3. Calculated CF values for the Apollo samples in Fig. 2.

Discussion: This analysis is just a small example highlighting the utility of the thermal infrared for not only determining surface temperature but also composition. It also shows the importance of tailoring your instrument to the mission. Figure 2 shows how the orbital instruments are designed to capture the majority of lunar surface compositions, and how LTM will provide a more detailed measurement of the range of composition that we have observed, improving upon Diviner. The landed instruments are well tailored to their landing sites: L-CIRiS will land at a pole, likely in a more highlands type region

similar to Apollo sample 67701; whereas LV-CIRiS will land on the Gruthuisen domes sampling a felsic volcanic material, which was not well-defined in the Diviner dataset (i.e. shortwave CF values).

Having these datasets for ground-based measurements (cm-scale) and orbital datasets (100 – 1000 m-scale) will allow us to gain insight into the importance of the scale of our measurements and gain detail we have not previously had from the Diviner instrument. We will also be able to use the landed missions to improve our orbital interpretations to enhance and refine global composition maps. Overall, we are headed into an excellent timeframe for gaining new information about the Moon through thermal infrared measurements at both varied spatial and spectral resolutions.

References: [1] Osterman et al., (2020) *LPSC #2702* [2] Donaldson Hanna (2025) *EPSC-DPS2025-1099* [3] Bowles et al., (2020) *LPSC #1380* [4] Paige et al., (2010) *SSR*. [5] Fraeman et al., (2020) *LPSC #1610* [6] Donaldson Hanna et al., (2017) *Icarus*, 283, 326-342 [7] Glotch et al., (2017) *LPSC #1688* [8] Greenhagen et al., (2010) *Science*, 329(5998), 1507-1509 [9] Shirley et al., (2026) *ESS*